

Awareness and Problems of Disable Students in Higher Educational Institutions in Anantapuramu District of Andhra Pradesh

M. Bhaskar Reddy¹

Research Scholar, Dept. of Sociology,
S.K. University, Anantapuramu-515003.

G. Venkataramana²

Professor, Head & Chairman, BOS, Dept. of Sociology,
S.K. University, Anantapuramu-515003.

Abstract:- The term 'Education' has a very broad connotation. It is very difficult to give its exact definition. There is no single objective which can cover the whole gamut of education with its various manifestations. According to one view, the term education has been derived from the Latin word 'educare' which means 'to bring up' or 'to raise'. According to this view, education is a process of imparting to an individual certain information and knowledge which society considers necessary. Various philosophers and thinkers-from Socrates to Dewey in the West, and Yajnavalkya to Gandhi in the East-have defined the term education in harmony with their own philosophy of life. As a result, divergent concepts and definitions of education have emerged. According to Rousseau, education does not simply mean imparting information or knowledge. For him, education is not an accretion from without; it is a spontaneous development of one's natural powers and capacities. For John Dewey, education is the development of capacities in the individual, which will enable him to control his environment and fulfill his potentialities. According to Gandhi, education is an all-around drawing out of the best in the body, mind and spirit of a child and a man. According to him, education begins from the moment of a child's conception to the moment of his death. In case of disable students especially in higher educational institutions have been facing number of problems. Hence, the present study is enlighten the perception of disable students on awareness and problems in higher educational institutions in Anantapuramu district of Andhra Pradesh State.

Keywords: Higher Education, Disability, Awareness, and Problems.

I. INTRODUCTION

Education is a major institution. It is created by the society to fulfill its task. This institution passes on stored experiences (culture/knowledge, etc.) from one generation to another to develop social efficiency of an individual, which ultimately helps the society to grow. This two-fold relationship between education and society- education being both the product and the producer of the social environment- is quite clear. It has been rightly said that the school is

created by society to re-create society'. Further, with the emergence of globalisation, change has become one of the major aspects which societies have required to keep up with, if they want to become developed. In this global neoliberal time, the role of higher education has become very important for economic development. Higher education institutions are now seen as key drivers in the knowledge economy. Consequently, this has led to economic recognition of higher education and brought higher education institutions /universities /colleges into the policy arena as catalysts within the society.

Similarly, research on institutions of higher education and higher education has been influenced mainly by human capital theory. This theory was developed by Schultz (1961). According to him, education should be looked upon as an investment for the individual, as well as for society, rather than being looked upon exclusively as consumption. This theory heavily influenced investments in the education sector as well as education policy and planning discourse. However, this theory was heavily criticised in the late 1960s and early 1970s. Bronchi (2003) states that increasing the level of education in a society can in circumstances lead to the high inequalities in income distribution. Another important challenge in the application of human capital theory is the failure to account for an increasing gap between growth of education people and knowledge base and the diminishing number of job opportunities to apply their increasing knowledge investment, more specifically in developing countries (Olaniyan and Okemakinde, 2008).

However, in this section we have focused mainly on theories of government policy - Human Rights based approach, and disability in theories of justice - Capability approach.

➤ Human Rights or Rights-Based Approach to Disability:

The emergence of the human rights approach coincided with the downfall of neo-liberal policies as a criticism against economic-centered development policy and practice (Seppanen, 2005). The human rights perspective to disability fundamentally means viewing individuals with disabilities as subjects of law. This approach locates disability within a paradigm of rights, that has been emerging since the United Nations Universal Declaration of Human Rights of 1948 (Rioux, and Carbert, 2003). As per

this Declaration, all people have certain political, economic, civil, social, cultural and development rights- regardless of various differences between individuals. Theoretically, this approach builds an analysis of how society marginalises people and how society can be adjusted to eradicate this marginalisation. In United Nations Human Rights Reports, Quinn and Degener (2002) defined individuals with disabilities as subjects and not as objects. It also views them as right holders. Similarly, it locates the problems outside the person and, especially, in the manner by which a range of social and economic processes accommodate the difference of disability or not as the case may be. Therefore, the debate about disability rights is largely linked to one about the place of difference in society.

This approach is closely related to the social model of disability which states that support for individuals with disability is not a question of humanity or charity. Instead, it is a basic human right that any person can claim. Thus, the rights perspective assumes that society is responsible to provide whatever mechanisms are necessary for people to realise their rights. Under the rights approach, persons with disabilities may get the provision of support services, devices, equipments to enable social and economic integration, self-determination, and the enjoyment of social and legal rights. As per this approach, all people have the right to participate and to exercise self-determination as equals in society. Another important aspect of this approach is that it applies guiding principles to ensure an acceptable development programming process such as participation, accountability, non-discrimination, empowerment and linkages to human rights standards (Martin and Boesen, 2007). It also focuses much on raising the levels of accountability and transparency by identifying the 'rights-holders' and the corresponding 'duty-bearers'. This framework should contribute to the improvement of the capacities of 'duty-bearers' to meet their responsibilities. Overall, it takes into account the duties of the various players' factors including individuals, local organisations, authorities, governments, aid donors and international institutions (See Human Rights in UNDP, 2003). This perspective also provides for the development of adequate laws, administrative practices, and mechanisms of equalisation and responsibilities both regarding entitlements and response to denials or violations of rights.

Despite the theoretical strength, this approach is not free from pitfalls (Katsui, 2008). The application of this approach to development is criticised as 'globalisation of policy making' with the use of Western power is taking place (Kennedy, 2004). Secondly, it is also criticised for its irresponsibility for intervention. For instance, human rights are inseparable and interdependent in principle. However, when it comes to practice, the operationalisation mechanism is feeble (Seppanen, 2005). For example, the international Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights states appropriate measure to be taken with 'available resource' and in the context of the full use of the maximum available resources (CESCR, 1990). When certain context is taken into account for operationalisation process, this weakness

becomes the primary challenge right away because situational analysis, identification of structural issues and other significant analysis are all missing thus hindering the implementers. Such analysis is very complex but yet undermined (Alston 2005). Thirdly, it has paid little attention to background social and political and historical conditions (Batiwala, 2007). Further, Kennedy (2004) claims that when changes rely too much on medical professionals and lawyers, the expected 'emancipator' impact of this approach cannot reach the emancipation of the concerned people by making necessary changes in practice. For instance, as far as people with disabilities are concerned, legal system and court are too often inaccessible due to illiteracy, lack of information, lack of awareness about rights, shortage of financial resources and or physical condition, and thus is then far from the concerned people who are supposed to benefit from the changes (Katsui, 2008).

➤ *Capability Approach to Disability:*

Similarly, political philosophers have developed several theories of justice which are aimed at proposing ideal social structures and processes as the philosophical base of a just society. In current years, theories of justice focus on the issue of disability, defining disability and critiquing earlier theories of justice designed to be universal-based on their failure to adequately account for disability. The Political philosopher Amartya Sen (1992) offers a different theory of justice to address disability and fairness for people with disabilities. According to him, when deciding whether two persons are equal in the context of social justice, one must reflect on not just resources and rights available to each individual, but also on each individual's ability to use their resources/goods and exercise their rights (Sen 1997). Differing personal abilities are important to decide the advantage. It is the fundamental aspect of Sen's interest in equality (Sen, 1992). Further Nussbaum (2003) articulates on how Sen's theory of justice translates into governmental treatment of disadvantaged groups, including people with disabilities. This approach suggests granting a right to a person; the State must guarantee that the person is provided the ability to use that right, which often necessitates the provision of 'affirmative material and institutional support, not simply a failure to impede'. Proactive support and special individualised treatment by the State may be essential to ensure the capability of exercising a government-granted right (Kimberlin, 2009). Consequently, the capability approach directs the government to think what the major barriers there are for full and effective empowerment of all citizens and to develop actions that eradicate these barriers (Nussbaum, 2003).

The capability approach has been taken up by scholars in various fields. Sen formulated the capability approach as a broad framework for disability (Kuno, 2008). This approach reflects a wide variety of factors within one framework, using the concept of capabilities and functioning. According to Sen, functioning is defined as an achievement, whereas capability is understood as the ability

to achieve (Sen 1987). Mitra (2003) stated that this framework helps to improve our understanding of disability and living conditions of disabled people by allowing us to analyse how disability results from the interaction between the personal characteristics (impairment, sex, reading skills, intelligence), available resources and the environment (physical, social, economic, political) of the individual, as well as the person's psychic states. This is particularly important in the analysis of well-being of persons with disabilities because their personal factors are varied and all very much influenced by social and environment factors (Mitra 2003; Terzi 2003). This kind of analysis helps to identify areas of intervention and means of intervention to be decided according to possibilities, appropriateness and preferences of the persons with disabilities (Kuno, 2008). Like any other theoretical approach, the capability approach has various limitations and shortcomings. According to Robeys (2003), there are various disputes around the capability approach whether it is too individualistic or not. Secondly, there is the debate about the critical or conservative nature of this approach, and related to that, the treatment of choice and power; and lastly, the discussions whether it leads to paternalism or inappropriate policies.

Out of these perspectives, the researcher believes that the capability approach has the potential to be a comprehensive framework of thought on issues and conditions which are related to students with disabilities in higher education by its provision of various useful implications. The capability approach offers an alternative space for social justice evaluation related to the notions of capabilities and freedom of choice. It argues that evaluation of well-being, poverty, inequality and justice, and the design of social policies and institutions should focus mainly on the individual's capabilities to function. The Capability Approach will be used to conceptualise and guide this study. The different components of the capability approach and its implication for this study are presented in the chapter on Methodology.

➤ *Concept of Education and Higher Education:*

According to UNESCO, the term 'higher education' includes "all types of studies, training, and training for research at the post-secondary level, provided as institutions of higher education by the competent State Authorities." Throughout the entire world, higher education is considered to be the key to both individual and societal aspirations (Laskar, 2010). For individuals, education beyond the secondary level is assumed to be the way to social esteem, better employment opportunities with good paying jobs, expanded life opportunities, and intellectual development. For societies, higher education is assumed to be the key to technology, productivity and other ingredients of international competitiveness and economic growth (Altbach & Johnstone, (Eds.). 1963). It is believed to be a major engine of social justice and equal opportunity and democracy.

Further, research on higher education began to accelerate with the rise of demand for higher education and

institutions (Clark, 1984). This demand required researchers and practitioners to look into the need to understand the role that universities play in society as higher education institutions. The research shows that most of the researchers and educators from all over the world agreed that universities play an active role within the society. Stepes et al. (2008) state that in the 19th century universities evolved from institutions that were responsible for preserving and transmitting knowledge to institutions that are charged with creating knowledge through research. In the later stage, during the industrial period, universities were seen as institutions that trained technical professionals (El-Ghali, 2011). From the last couple of decades, researchers have started to state that universities have an added role to perform, namely, contributing directly to society through acting as catalysts (Gibbons, 1999). Similarly Seidel (1991) highlighted five important functions of higher education institutions in his study. They: (i) provide training and education; (ii) provide professional training in professions including medicine, law and teaching; (iii) provide regional development, (iv) develop international contacts; and (v) conduct research and social function in fostering the intellectual and social development of society (El-Ghali, 2011). Further, UNESCO (1988) also highlighted the importance of higher education in contributing to the process of national development and progress.

In summary, all the researchers have concluded that higher education institutions play an active role in the training of productive intellectual resources for the development of society (Mendivil, 2002). Thus, these institutions are charged with the responsibility of training people and generating knowledge that can, in turn, trigger national development.

➤ *Objectives:*

- To know the theoretical background of higher education in India
- To study the awareness levels of the disable students
- To analyse the problems of the disable students in Anantapuramu district of Andhra Pradesh'

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

➤ *Setting of the Study:*

The present study is depending on empirical analysis. The researcher has selected 150 sample respondents who are disable and studying in higher learning institutions like Degree colleges, and Universities in Anantapuramu district. The researcher has used purposeful sampling techniques. The data were collected through a structure questionnaire from the sample disable students from the Anantapuramu district. And also secondary data were collected from the various sources.

➤ *Data Collection Instrument:*

A self structured questionnaire was used to assess the prevalence of psychosocial problems, their risk factors and knowledge levels among people with Disability students.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1 Students Details by Impairment & Gender

S.No	Variables		Education		Sub-total	Grand Total
			Further Studies	Jobs		
1	Gender	Male	61 (61.61)	38 (38.39)	99 (66.00)	150 (100.00)
		Female	29 (56.86)	22 (43.14)	51 (34.00)	
2	Impairment	Orthopedic	66 (61.11)	42 (38.89)	108 (72.00)	150 (100.00)
		Visual	26 (61.90)	16 (38.10)	42 (28.00)	

Source: Field Survey

The present table 1 demonstrated that cross verification of disable students Gender, Nature of impairment, University with their goals in Ananthapuramu district of Andhra Pradesh. It is noticed from the study that 61.61 per cent of male students have expressed that after education they concentrate on further education and rest of the male disabled students will enter in to any organization as an employee in the study. While female disabled students were found that 56.86 per cent were focus on further education after present education and 43.14 per cent of them to see as an employee in organization.

When focus on nature of impairment and goals of disable students seen that the relationship between two visible. It can be found that the 61.11 per cent represents (66 students) orthopedic disable students were focused on further studies and 38.89 per cent were expressed that they focus on reaching their goals, according to visual impairments students respondents-61.50 respondents were focused on further studies and rest of them i.e., 38.10 per cent were noticed that they entered into organization as a employee.

Graph 1 Students Details According to Further Study and Jobs Gender-Wise.

Graph 2 Students Details According to Further Study and Jobs Also Type of Impairment

Table 2 Activities Through Internet N= 66

S.No	Activity	Frequency	Percentage
1	Scholarship updates/Financial information	33	50.00
2	Current information	29	45.00
3	Listening Music	52	80.00

Source: Field Survey

The internet using for other purposes such as seeking information regarding updates of scholarship status, financial information and listening music etc. It can be clearly noticed that half of the percentage of the disable students have been using internet for update of their scholarship/financial information, 45 per cent of the respondents were noticed that they collect current affairs by using internet and majority of the respondents have been using internet for listening music and relax from the stress.

Graph 3 Students Details According to Internet Activities

Table 3 Students' Details According to Ramp Facility N=108

S.No	Facility of Ramp	Frequency	Percentage
1	Yes	108	100.00
2	No	00	00.00
	Total	108	100.00

Source: Field Survey

The educational institutions were established and provided to some of the special facilities with reference to disable students at all levels. This right is provided by the Indian Constitution and same is facilitated by the every organization. According to this context, the opinion was sought from the disable students about Ramp facility at college or university. The table found that all colleges and universities have been facilitated ramp facility to the disable students all respondents were agreed above facilities.

Graph 4 Students Details According Ramp Facility

Table 4 Students' Details According to Lift/Elevator Facility N=108

S.No	Facility of Lift/Elevator	Frequency	Percentage
1	Yes	00	00.00
2	No	108	100.00
	Total	108	100.00

Source: Field Survey

It is another facility i.e., Lift/Elevator facility at more than one floor in colleges or universities. It is unfortunately noticed that there is no providing such kind of facility at any college or university in the study area. It can be concluded from the study that the colleges are not taken any risk or financial burden in case of providing such facility even there is no much supervision by the state authorities in the study area.

Graph 5 Students Details According to University-Wise Lift/Elevator

Table 5 Students' Details According to Transport Facility N=108

S.No	Transport Facility	Frequency	Percentage
1	Yes	44	40.74
2	No	64	59.26
	Total	108	100.00

Source: Field Survey

The State and Central Government have been providing various facility to the visually and orthopedic disable students and development of them without any problem at educational institutions. In this context, the researcher has point out that transportation facility is provided by the colleges, university or Government. According to this question 40.74 per cent of the student respondents have stated that – yes- transportation facility have been providing by either Government/ institutions at study institutions and rest of them, 59.26 per cent were expressed that there is no providing transportation facility by the Government/colleges/universities in the study area.

Graph 6 Students Details According To Transport Facility

Table 6 Students’ Details According to Footpaths Within the Campus N=108

S.No	Footpath Facility	Frequency	Percentage
1	Yes	32	29.63
2	No	76	70.37
	Total	108	100.00

Source: Field Survey

The table 6 portrayal that the opinion of the sample disable students on satisfaction footpath facility which are provided and facilitated by the colleges and universities. In this context, 29.63 per cent of the sample disabled students were expressed that ‘yes’ it indicate that colleges/universities have established footpath at college/university premises. And it is clear noticed that majority of the sample higher education disable students not agreed on said facility.

Graph 7 Students Details According to Footpath Facility

Table 7 Students Details According to Special Parking Areas in Campus N=108

S.No	Special Parking Areas	Frequency	Percentage
1	Yes	00	00.00
2	No	108	100.00
	Total	108	100.00

Source: Field Survey

In case of special parking area should also provide to the disable students at college environment and it is mandatory to all disable student colleges. According to this- the study implies that there is no providing such kind of facility by the any college/campus. So, the study will recommended that there is urgent need to provide separate parking area for easy moving of the disable students in the study area.

Graph 8 Students Details According Special Parking Facility

Table 8 Students Perception about Classrooms

S.No	Opinion on Classrooms	Frequency	Percentage
1	Friendly	39	26.00
2	Not Friendly	111	74.00
	Total	150	100.00

Source: Field Survey

The “accessibility was measured by the on campus accessibility to physical support to class room, libraries/labs. Then students use nearly different ways to move around in educational institutions. Some use crutches, canes, walkers, wheelchairs and scooters. The education institutions need to make should that the class room/labs are arranged in such a way that these can accommodate the student with mobility need. Academic accessibility is important, not only for orthopedically impaired students, but also for students with visual impairment for their active participation at higher education. In this study the researcher categorized students responses into two category, such as friendly and not-friendly. Here the term friendly means those who are having disabled friendly environment or easy access, where as not friendly means those who faced physical barriers due to absence of ramps, lifts and elevators”. The present table 8 depicts that the perception of the disabled students with orthopedic and visually impairment on academic accessibility in their respective universities.

The present table stated that majority of the sample disabled students were expressed their opinion that their university has not provided accessibility to the class room and it is represents 74 per cent, and only 26 per cent (39 disabled students) of the respondents have accepted that the class room environment is eco-friendly mobility.

Graph 9 Students Opinion on Class Room

Table 9 Students Perception on Library N=150

S.No	Opinion on Library	Frequency	Percentage
1	Friendly	55	36.67
2	Not Friendly	95	63.33
	Total	150	100.00

Source: Field Survey

It is another opined that the researcher put a question to the sample respondents regarding their accessibility at the library is every colleges/universities. It is further found that 63.33 per cent represents 95 students with disabled are expressed that there no much accessibility at libraries of educational institutions while 36.67 per cent represents 55 students respondents were provide positive response above said statement it means they freely accessibility at libraries in the study area.

Graph 10 Students Opinion on Library

Table 10 Students Perception on Hostels

S.No	Opinion on Hostel	Frequency	Percentage
1	Friendly	113	75.33
2	Not Friendly	37	24.67
	Total	150	100.00

Source: Field Survey

The present study was noticed from the above table 10 that the opinion of the respondents on the hostel environment at their college/universities. It can be noticed that the data were shown positive dimension to the disable students point of view- it means the university hostels were provided with disable students with friendly nature and it is proved that 75.33 per cent were agreed on the statement and one of fourth position of the higher education students were not agreed on above students.

The study is clearly concluded from the study that the disable students have received hostel room in ground floor which are needed and requirement of disable students and authorities were also supporting to this students in the study area.

Graph 11 Students Opinion on Hostels

Table 11 Students Perception on Academic & Admin Building

S.No	Opinion on Academic & Admin Building	Frequency	Percentage
1	Friendly	38	25.33
2	Not Friendly	112	74.67
	Total	150	100.00

Source: Field Survey

When the student's perception on academic accessibility was related to the type of university, there was not much significant difference in student perception based on type of the university in relation to the provision of academic accessibility. The present table 11 can be observed from the statistical data regarding academic administration buildings- there is no friendly treated by the administration and academic authorities with 74.67 per cent and only 25.33 per cent have stated that they treated as a friendly nature at university/college level. It can be concluded from the study that the disable students don't have friendly academic accessibility other than accessibility.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The higher education is play a predominant role for development of impairment people life. If the acquired higher qualifications- they will get better position in the society in both public and private sectors. In this process, how they completed their education at higher learning institutions. It can be noticed that the present concluded that they have been facing number of problems at college and university level. The government will initiate and make a favourable decision for upliftment of the disable students in drought prone area like Anantapuramu district.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Konur, O. (2006). Teaching disabled students in high-er education. *Teaching in Higher Education*, 11, 351-363.
- [2]. Paley, N. (1995) *Finding art's place: Experiments in contemporary education and culture*. New York: Routledge.
- [3]. Rao, S. (2004). Faculty attitudes and students with disabilities in higher education: A literature review. *College Student Journal*, 38, 191-199.
- [4]. Robinson, K. (2001). *All our futures: Creativity, culture and education*. Sudbury, England: National Advisory Committee on Creative and Cultural Education: Department for Education and Employment.
- [5]. Sarason, S. B. (1990). *The challenge of art to psychology*. New Haven, CT: Yale University Press.
- [6]. Silver, P., Bourke, A., & Strehorn, K. C. (2006). Universal instructional design in higher education: An approach for inclusion. *Equity & Excellence in Education*, 31(2), 47-51.
- [7]. Ware, L. P. (2002). A moral conversation on disability: Risking the personal in educational contexts.
- [8]. *Hypatia: A Journal of Feminist Philosophy*, 17, 143-172